

Role of psychology in human resource management

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Abstract

Where human resource management is present, psychological problems arise. This is why increasing focus is put on the use of psychological sciences and tools in management. The goal of this article is to present preliminary conclusions on the role of psychology in human resource management in organizations.

Introduction

There are connections between psychology and organization. The primary component illustrating HRM theory and practice from its more traditional employee management beginnings is the combination of psychology and human behavior management. In the psychology of management, the human element is seen as the primary focus, a fundamental aspect of its significance. When we study psychology management, we examine the individual's psychology, his numerous aspects, and most importantly, how his mental actions affect his activity, which in turn affects his psychology and behavior. This area of psychology studies how people think and behave when they plan, organize, manage, and control a group activity. It is called the psychology of management.

The integration between the management of human resources and psychology is arguably the prime factor delineating HRM theory and practice from its more traditional personnel management origins. Selection of the personnel has long been recognized as a key activity within HR and this article seeks to explore the extent to which its practice provides evidence of such strategic alignment.

Literature review

After defining management, Seyidov (2000) demonstrates how psychology and management are related. Management is the science of coordinating an organization's resources to achieve its goals. A person's psychological characteristics, which are reflected in his behavior, are always there wherever he is. When studying the psychology of management, we look at the psychology of the individual, his conduct, and—above all—how his mentality affects his activity and how his action affects his psychology and behavior. The study of a person's mental characteristics and behavior during planning, organizing, managing, and controlling group activities is known as the psychology of management.

In management psychology, the human factor is seen as the focal point, its essence, and its core. As managers study people in the context of specific practical psychology activities, they are always confronted with issues that require improvement in both the professional activity and the individual performing it. Four core issues or fundamental questions of the psychology of management—motivation, leadership, interpersonal relations, and people selection—have received the most attention from Seyidov (2000) among this range of issues.

Analysis

Psychology is a very diverse field that includes a wide range of methods for examining behavior and thought processes. When Dr. Walter Dill Scott of the United States of America discussed the

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potential for applying psychological concepts to the world of business in 1901, it was born as a subfield of psychology. The third or fourth most popular area of psychology is management psychology.

The two fundamental importance of psychology in HRM

- The goal of psychology in HRM is to comprehend how people behave in the workplace, how they can become more productive, happy, pleased, and rewarded, and how these results can be increased.

- Studying how an organization can grow and endure through the use of psychological theories, research, and interventions in order to create and execute workable solutions to address organizational difficulties

The term "management psychology" describes the application of psychological concepts and methods in a professional setting. Enhancing workplace dynamics, raising employee satisfaction, and identifying and resolving issues are the objectives. Although industrial-organizational psychology is the most common name for this field, it is also known as IO psychology, work psychology, business psychology, and occupational psychology. Managers continually deal with issues that require improvement for both the professional work and the person who performs it, as they study the individual in the context of the tangible practical actions of psychology. It tries to understand the human problems that have arisen as a result of tremendous expansion of industry in the last few decades. It is defined as the study of man and his behavior with the aid of scientific methodology. The Science of behavior, (what we do) and mental processes, (thoughts, sensations, perceptions, dreams, beliefs, and feelings). Organizational psychology has the potentiality to contribute to the productivity of industry and business, on one hand and achieving greater effectiveness.

Below, we'll be looking at how a better knowledge of organizational psychology may help HR, as well as how teams can use psychological tools and insights to enhance the employee lifecycle and drive business success.

Organizational psychology can result in more successful recruiting and talent management. Psychological evaluations are one method that psychology is used throughout the recruiting process. Since the 1880s, psychometric tests have been used to ensure neutrality throughout the recruiting process. Employing such a rigorous technique to assess candidates' mental capacities and behavioral patterns gives hiring managers' confidence that they are picking people with the necessary knowledge and skills. However, even before the interview process begins, HR professionals may utilize these assessments to establish a baseline of their core and desired values for the job. Psychology may assist identify what the employment entails and what is required, resulting in a more effective job definition.

Psychology is also being utilized to improve organizational diversity in corporations, with psychological studies guiding the development of more inclusive hiring practices. For example, the British Psychological Society (BPS) has advocated for HR departments to address the requirements of neurodiverse individuals, such as those with dyslexia, attention deficit disorder, or autism, during their procedures. In addition, the CIPD advocated in its Neurodiversity at Work study that HR managers be more aware of unusual body language during interviews or skip the interview stage completely in favor of gamified techniques to be inclusive of autistic persons.

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Organizational psychology can assist in boosting employee engagement.

Human resource experts may apply psychological theory and research into actual workplace actions to promote progress in these areas. Today, more government agencies and businesses use occupational and organizational psychology than ever before, and HR departments that use its techniques frequently report increases in employee engagement and productivity. This is accomplished, in part, through recognition programs. An organization with a recognition-rich culture sees a 29% gain in profit and a 72% decrease in employee attrition. This is because recognizing employees, whether through public acclaim or private remarks from a senior staff member, has been shown to improve employee engagement.

Resolving low employee engagement can help a company differentiate itself from competitors. Research indicates that businesses with higher employee engagement scores expand more robustly than those with lower rankings. Better morale, higher production, and lower employee turnover are all associated with more engagement.

Enhancing employee wellness can be achieved through the application of organizational psychology.

Employee welfare is now more important to organizations than it has ever been. According to the CIPD, companies have a basic responsibility for caring out for the physical and mental well-being of their employees. Research indicates that psychological risks are currently the major threats to employee health.

Several psychological techniques can be used by HR directors and managers to promote a supportive work environment that places a high priority on mental health. This involves fostering an environment that lessens the stigma associated with mental health, allowing people to discuss their struggles more openly. Mental health is highly stigmatized; 40% of Scottish employees surveyed said discussing a mental health issue could endanger their employment.

According to a research titled "The Role of Psychology in Human Resources Management," which was published in the European Journal of Psychology, including psychology into the management plan necessitates a strategy in and of itself. Four key questions—motivation, leadership, interpersonal relationships, and personnel selection—are used by the report's author, Talibova Rasim, a psychology professor at Azerbaijan University of Languages, to demonstrate how HRM and psychology are related. The latter, they acknowledge, is where "management and psychology most closely intertwine."

In the report, Rasim outlines a number of methods that HR managers may use to find more qualified job candidates by utilizing their knowledge of psychology. The first method that was discussed was interviews.

interviews

According to the paper, "The face-to-face selection interview is the traditional method," "Yet it is fraught with problems of subjectivity, interpersonal judgment, interpretation and misinterpretation."

Rasim notes that judges are examining interviews in external inspections more closely in order to identify incompetent hiring, which may discourage businesses from depending on them as much. Nonetheless, certain intangible checks are permitted during the interview process. According to the survey, for example, interviews help candidates stand out from one another, assess sociability and teamwork, and give candidates an opportunity to showcase themselves rather than be "judged mechanically."

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Psychometric tests

HR managers can more thoroughly assess a candidate's cognitive and self-reporting abilities, such as communicative, numerical, and logical aptitude, by using bought or proprietary tests. HR managers may more quickly identify how well a person's skill set matches the one required by the open position by gathering referenceable data on various talents.

simulations

HR managers may witness candidates in action by designing fictitious but convincing working scenarios (which might vary from giving presentations to issue solving). These insights allow the expert to better analyze the feasibility of any certain applicant.

Biographical analysis

Rasim noted that there are many levels of biographical examination, which can vary from as serious as a background check to as casual as a lengthy interview. However, the goal of the study remains the same: to better understand the applicant and where they come from.

Conclusion

Organizational Psychology is a subfield of psychology that studies people, and their behavior in a working environment. The settings in which people work and function are helpful in gaining a better understanding of the individual's behavior and how this behavior can change, influenced and enhanced in benefiting the organization and its employees. Industrial psychology focuses basically on three aspects i.e. worker, the work that is being performed and the context in which the work is to be performed.

Psychology has a lot to offer in terms of concepts for making work more enjoyable and meaningful while also preventing psychological damage. As a result, the finest HR executives should devote themselves to ensuring the workplace is operationally productive and healthy. If you're an HR professional trying to further your career or improve your organization's effectiveness, learning more about the human mind and how it affects and is influenced by the workplace may be the appropriate move.

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